

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP2 – Outcome Driven Healthcare

D2.6 Workshop for HTA and payer community: demonstrate the OMOP-CDM for generating meaningful HTA + payer evidence

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

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V0.4	19/12/2020	Comments
V1.0	21/12/2020	Final Draft for consortium review
V1.1	11/01/2021	Final Version

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Health technology assessment (HTA) is widely used throughout Europe and elsewhere to make decisions about the reimbursement and/or pricing of healthcare technologies including new medicines. Several countries require evidence on cost-effectiveness and budget impact and so estimates of healthcare use and costs are important. This poses challenges to companies generating such evidence in support of their products from multiple countries and datasets. EHDEN is a federated network of data sources mapping to the OMOP common data model (OMOP-CDM). This has the potential to facilitate companies in generating high quality real word evidence by improving the interoperability of data and support the application of common analytical code across databases from different countries. Such evidence may be valuable to the HTA community when making reimbursement decisions.

We organised a virtual, half-day workshop titled ‘Federated data networks and health technology assessment’ to introduce EHDEN and the OMOP-CDM and its use to generate real world evidence (RWE) to HTA bodies. This involved the presentation of regulatory and early HTA use cases. We also asked attendees for feedback on where they saw the potential for the use of OMOP-CDM and EHDEN in HTA settings and which areas and applications they felt EHDEN should prioritise in the next year. In general, HTA bodies see RWE as complementary to clinical trial evidence and were particularly interested in areas where clinical trial evidence may be unavailable or limited, such as rare diseases and medical devices. They also would value RWE which supports challenging areas in HTA, such as assessment of advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs) and providing evidence to support outcome-based managed entry arrangements. The need for transparently reported, high quality RWE studies was also emphasised.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Common data models (CDMs) embedded with large data networks may aid the generation of real world evidence (RWE) to support health technology assessment (HTA) procedures across multiple jurisdictions. At present, the use and awareness in HTA organisations of such approaches may not yet be lower than in the regulatory community. Therefore, one of the aims of WP2 is to engage with HTA bodies to demonstrate the evidence network and associated analytical tools currently being developed as part of EHDEN. We organised a virtual, half-day workshop titled ‘Federated data networks and health technology assessment’ on Friday 27 November 2020. This report details the workshop proceedings held in November 2020. The workshop was attended by 28 participants, that included staff of different HTA bodies, people working in the pharmaceutical industry, patient advocacy organisations, staff from drug regulatory authorities, and academic researchers. The program was as follows:

Time (GMT)	Title	Presenter/chair (institution)
09:00-09:15	Welcome and Introductions	Nige Hughes (Janssen)
09:15-09:35	Introduction to OMOP and EHDEN	Peter Rijnbeek (Erasmus University Medical Center) / Jacoline Bouvy (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence)
09:35- 09:55	EHDEN regulatory use cases	Dani Prieto Alhambra (University of Oxford)
09:55-10.05	questions and discussion	
10:05-10:25	EMA perspective	Gianmario Candore (European Medicines Agency)
10:25-10:35	Questions and discussion	
10:35-10:45	Break	
10:45-11:10	EHDEN HTA use cases	Seamus Kent (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence)
11:10-11:30	Industry perspective	Mark Rozenbaum (Pfizer)
11:30-11:50	Group discussion	Jacoline Bouvy (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence)
11:50-12:00	Reflections & future opportunities	Nige Hughes (Janssen)

The aims of this workshop were to demonstrate the capabilities of OMOP-CDM and a federated data network to generate meaningful evidence for the HTA community. The key strengths of transparency, standardised analysis, rapid delivery of results and compliance with data privacy regulations would be highlighted, along with some limitations of the approach, such as mapped data potentially having less granularity than the source data. A further aim was to elicit feedback from the attendees in several key areas, including

- what could be learned from using OMOP-CDM in the regulatory setting?
- what is the potential of OMOP and EHDEN in the HTA setting?
- which disease areas and applications should EHDEN prioritise in the next year?

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2. WORKSHOP

The workshop covered several key areas, which are discussed in more detail below.

OMOP CDM and EHDEN

The EHDEN project leads, Nigel Hughes and Peter Rijnbeek presented a general overview of the OMOP-CDM and EHDEN. They highlighted that the benefits of using a common data model are to harmonise the data from different sources to allow it to be useable in a standard fashion. This can support reproducibility by allowing evidence from different sources to be examined using standardised analytical tools. It can also allow the robustness of the evidence to be examined by systematically conducting sensitivity analyses using a range of analytical techniques. It was also noted that non-standard analytical tools could also be developed where required by the specific research question or data source, a good understanding of the source data is required to determine when this approach is appropriate.

A key aspect of the process is mapping from the source data to the common data model. It was noted that this process is challenging but is subject to quality control measures and is increasingly being automated alongside standardised report of quality control checks to ensure the process is transparent. It was also highlighted that the CDM is constantly being improved and is designed so that databases can be refreshed. The process is becoming increasingly automated, for example the IPCI primary care database, which contains over 2 million records was refreshed automatically overnight. As well as being a rapid process the mapping code is openly available, meaning the mapping process is highly transparent.

THE EHDEN project was also introduced. EHDEN aims to build a large scale European federated data network standardised to the OMOP-CDM. This allows real world health care data to be discovered and analysed rapidly. Analysis is supported by the development of standardised tools and dashboards to visualise results. The EHDEN network is developing and currently consists of 65 data partners with over 200 million patient records. It was highlighted that one of the advantages of using a federated data network is that it gives the EHDEN platform the potential to allow results from several data sources to be analysed by bringing the analytical code to the data locally, ensuring that data owners are still in control of their data. This ensures that data governance regulations (such as GDPR) can be adhered to as only aggregate results are shared and there is no exchange of patient identifiable information.

Regulatory use cases and perspective

Dani Prieto Alhambra presented work from the EHDEN project on a use case where the OMOP-CDM was used to perform a population-level effect estimate [1]. This example demonstrated the comparative risks of hydroxychloroquine (with or without azithromycin) and the study identified concerning cardiotoxicity safety signals for the combination, which resulted in regulatory action by the EMA. There are further studies ongoing on databases which contain data on COVID-19 patients looking at safety and comparative efficacy of drugs in different classes. This use case demonstrated that meaningful, high quality results can be delivered rapidly, which is a major advantage of federated studies.

Gianmario Candore presented the experience of the EMA on OMOP-CDM. This included a validation study examining whether results in the prevalence of use of codeine in children from a source database could be replicated after mapping data to the common data model [2]. Estimates were similar and did not affect interpretation of the data, furthermore after improvements were made to the mapping process identical results were obtained. While such validation studies are not necessarily generalisable to other data sources or research areas, they gave valuable insight into potential issues and also highlight how refinements to the

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mapping process can improve the validity of data mapped to the OMOP CDM. A further regulatory example looked at the number of patients using ranitidine who may be at risk of exposure to a potential carcinogen. This example highlighted the speed of analysis in multiple databases using a CDM approach – with results drawing from 6 databases reported only 2 months after protocol approval. The study protocol is publicly available, along with the code required to run the analysis [3]. Results were disseminated transparently by making them available in a web application that allowed results to be browsed by database [4].

The EMA’s plans for its Data Analysis and Real-World Interrogation Network (DARWIN EU) were also outlined. This is envisaged as a federated data network supported by a third-party coordination centre to manage the data and ensure data quality standards are met. This may allow rapid analysis of RWE across the network using standard tools to answer key research questions which impact committee opinion. The DARWIN EU business case includes the use of the network along the full lifecycle of the product, therefore use cases will be relevant for a range of areas beyond safety, such as rare diseases. It was confirmed that national competent authorities will be involved in the development of DARWIN EU as part of the coordination steering group and the European Commission and HTA bodies would be consulted as key stakeholders throughout the development of DARWIN EU. It was also noted that DARWIN EU would include a use case that covered application in HTA.

HTA Use cases

In addition to the benefits already discussed above for regulatory use cases, a federated network is valuable to HTA bodies because it allows them to focus on results within their own jurisdiction or to analyse patients in databases from other jurisdictions, including only relevant patients with similar baseline characteristics.

Seamus Kent presented the work he led on the HTA use case in EHDEN. This involved estimating the annual rate of COPD exacerbations and primary care visits in patients with COPD by disease severity in UK and the Netherlands. While this was found to be feasible, some challenges were encountered that required the use of bespoke coding solutions as there were some differences between the two databases used in the study. This included differences in how data relating to primary care visits was pre-processed and how it was mapped to the common data model. This means that the number of primary care visits may not be estimated correctly.

The use case highlighted the potential of federated data networks and a CDM, but it was noted that further development was needed to ensure that research questions relevant to HTA could be addressed. EHDEN partners are preparing a paper for submission to a peer reviewed journal that will describe the use case and highlight key recommendations. For example, improvements to the mapping of health economic data could be made by expanding or improving vocabularies relating to health economics and involving HTA professionals in quality assuring the mapping process to ensure it meets HTA needs. The development of analytical tools and dashboards to support HTA use cases (for example long-term survival extrapolation) would also be beneficial and something that EHDEN WP2 and WP4 will take forward in the next year of the project.

Industry perspective

Mark Rozenbaum presented several areas where the use of a federated data network aligned to a common data model could be of benefit from an industry perspective. Several of these are relevant prior to the submission of an HTA dossier and include characterisation of the relevant patient population, identifying existing treatment practices, burden of disease and resource use studies and validation of the economic

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model and the key assumption underpinning it. There are also applications after the HTA process, for example in managing outcome-based pricing schemes, budget impact and supporting ongoing contracting.

Outcome-based agreements were identified as a promising area because some of the barriers to making more use of outcomes-based agreements such as data governance and the lack of mutually agreed outcome measures could potentially be overcome using the common data model within a federated network. While some challenges may still remain, for example implementing infrastructure where a trusted third party can manage such agreements – EDHEN potentially provides a framework where this can be achievable.

Open discussion

Several themes emerged from open discussion on the potential of OMOP-CDM and EDHEN.

Value of RWD/RWE to HTA bodies

There was a consensus among the HTA/payer representatives at the meeting that randomised controlled trial (RCT) data would still be considered “the gold standard.” HTA bodies see the use of RWD as “complementary” to RCT data but there are situations in which data generated outside clinical trial settings is useful. One example is when the length of the trial is too short to capture clinical outcomes of interest. One HTA representative stated that because of this there is a “need to look beyond a confirmatory trial.”

It was recognised that in some areas, such as rare diseases, clinical trial data may be unavailable and that RWD is a valuable source of evidence. One attendee stated that in such cases where the evidence base is limited the “ability to combine data from different sources is a priority.” One attendee emphasised that increase utilisation of RWD should not be used as an excuse for companies to avoid conducting trials and that RCTs should always be conducted where possible. The need for “absolutely excellent RWE studies” was highlighted, with efforts to encourage good practice, increase transparency and drive improvements in quality and standards seen as important goals. Another attendee identified medical devices as another area of high unmet need where the evidence based is limited and cautioned that looking at rare diseases alone would be too narrow a focus.

One of the key areas of value highlighted by attendees was in assessing long-term treatment outcomes, particularly for technologies such as advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs), which may come with a high one-off initial cost. Assessments of agreed upon long term outcomes would be useful for managing outcomes-based pricing arrangements to attempt to address barriers which may prevent these arrangements working, such as prohibitive financial and resource requirements.

One attendee also noted that we need to specifically “bring up questions being addressed by HTA bodies now” rather than simply focusing on study types which are well established. Nevertheless, they recognised the advantages of being able to discuss evidence openly and across multiple countries.

Policy considerations

One attendee stated that from a policy perspective EDHEN and OMOP is a “good starting point” but the proof of the approach would be “five years ahead.” This was because it is not yet clear how the evidence generated would influence decisions, particularly if RWE contradicts the results of RCTs. There was a perception that as results for efficacy may be expected to be worse than the results from RCTs, there would need to be a high level of confidence in the quality of the evidence to enable difficult policy decision to be made.

One presenter suggested that there is a “vicious circle” preventing uptake of RWE for HTA purposes, that the methods used to analyse RWD are not fit for purpose for HTA evaluations because HTA bodies are not

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perceived to use RWE for decisions. It was noted that overcoming this will take a lot of work – and may involve challenging a prevailing view that “the RWE study must be wrong.”

Operational and technical considerations

Attendees made several operational and technical comments and queries. Several of these have been discussed in earlier sections of this report, including potential loss of data during the mapping process, whether mapping is a one-off process and data governance issues (such as GDPR).

An additional question was how EDHEN decided on relevant research priorities and queries. It was highlighted that studies are based on relevant research questions that are important to the clinical community. Collaboration with the wider ODHSI community is also important particularly in priority areas such as COVID-19 where performing high quality studies at pace is important. Examples from the regulatory area, such as the ranitidine study described above were also identified as a driver for research. Participation by HTA bodies in ODHSI activities was encouraged. There are several possibilities for how an ODHSI network around HTA could be initiated (for example through participation in the ODHSI forums) and this could be a way forward to ensure the needs of HTA organisations are met.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Summary of findings

In general, HTA bodies see RWE as complementary to clinical trial evidence and were particularly interested in areas where clinical trial evidence may be unavailable or limited, such as rare diseases and medical devices. They also would value RWE which supports challenging areas in HTA, such as assessment of ATMPs and providing evidence to support outcome-based managed entry arrangements.

HTA bodies identified the ability to draw on evidence from a wide array of sources in a transparent manner was seen as being valuable, but noted that studies would have to be considered to be high quality to meet their evidence needs. The potential of the EHDEN network to help facilitate this was recognised. It was also noted that the policy implications of increasing the use of RWE would have to be considered, for example considering how decisions are made if efficacy results based on RWE are worse than the RCTs used as the basis for reimbursement.

There was also significant interest and a desire from HTA bodies to be involved in EMA activities relating to DARWIN EU. Learning from and contributing to this project may help to highlight the value of participating in the EHDEN network (and vice versa).

Recommendations

- EHDEN should continue to engage with the HTA community to ensure that the evidence needs of HTA bodies are met. The forthcoming publication in PharmacoEconomics on the potential of common data models and HTA will be an important vehicle for further engagement and awareness with HTA experts. A further workshop is planned as part of deliverable D2.7.
- Encourage engagement between HTA bodies, HTA researchers, and the ODHSI community (forum), and also regulatory initiatives such as DARWIN EU
- Seek HTA input in use cases which have been identified as important – such as rare diseases and outcome-based managed entry agreements
- Highlight what EHDEN can do for HTA now – not just 5 years down the line.

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- (4) Web application for exploring the results of the drug utilization study of ranitidine available at: <https://mi-erasmusmc.shinyapps.io/ResultsExplorer/> (accessed December 2020).